

Communication for Affiliation : An Indicative Approach to Understand Blogging

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Sharing or affiliation has long since been established as one of the basic human activities. Maslow's hierarchy of needs listed belongingness as one of the basic human needs. In his theory of motivation, McClelland (1961) said that people are motivated by one of three things: the need for achievement, the need for power or the need for affiliation. Persons motivated by the need for affiliation seek relationships and interactions with a variety of different types of people. Besides these two, research literature is abound on need for affiliation as important to human well being. Researchers generally agree that there is a definite urge in people to share their emotional experiences whether positive or negative. If there is one medium that encourages and enables affiliation the most, it is the blog. Millions of bloggers all over the world are sharing their lives with each other. Although this sharing (affiliation) has been happening for a long time now first it was the email, then the homepage on the World Wide Web, then the chat, complete with text, voice and video the blogs have now taken over the virtual lives in virtual worlds. Blogs have, in one way, changed nothing significant other than perhaps the interface, i.e. the way people share the same old text, sounds and images with each other in the virtual space. The change however, is in the presence of the individual. In what is now referred to as blogosphere, an individual is not lost in countless pseudonyms of a chatroom, nor is his individuality hostage to pressures of online community or user-group. Besides, the blog as a medium is truly "democratic". This study, being an exploratory analysis, explains the meaning of blogs before going on to explore with the help of secondary data that why this is a medium that deserves to be talked about and why people use blogs. This would be followed by an explanatory analysis on what makes blogging important when there are already so many other means of communication. This paper is dedicated to the millions of bloggers all over the world who are sharing their lives with each other. Yes this sharing been happening for a long time now first it was the email, then the homepage on the World Wide Web, then the chat, complete with text, voice and video. Now the blogs have taken over the virtual lives in virtual worlds.

Keywords: Affiliation, blogging, virtual space, exploratory analysis

Introduction

Blogs have, in one way, changed nothing significantly other than perhaps the interface, that is how people share the same old text, sounds and images with each other in the virtual space. The change however, is in the presence of the individual. In what is now referred to as blogosphere, an individual is not lost in countless pseudonyms of a chatroom, nor is his individuality hostage to pressures of online community or user-group. Besides, the blog as a medium is truly "democratic"⁷. Although, there is no conclusive data on the profile of this individual, but a random shuffling through the blogs would suggest that most of these are written by the young. Thus, it suggests that the youth that we are talking about here is the champion of the individuality. No

wonder it is this (you)th that the Time magazine named the person of the year for 2006⁸.

Before going any further let me explain for the non-bloggers One, what a blog is i.e. its meaning, its content and its purpose; and Secondly, why is this a medium that deserves to be talked about i.e. a little bit of number crunching. This would be followed by an explanation on what makes blogging important when we have so many other means of communication?

The term "blog" is derived from "Web log." A blog is a user-generated website where entries are made in journal style and displayed in a reverse chronological order. Blogs often provide commentary or news on a particular subject, such as food, politics, or local news; (while) some function as more personal online diaries. A typical blog combines text, images, and links to other blogs, web pages, and other media related to its topic. The ability for readers to leave comments in an interactive format is an important part of many blogs. "Blog" can also be used as a verb, meaning to maintain or add content to a blog⁹.

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Early weblogs were simply manually updated components of common websites. However, the evolution of tools to facilitate the production and maintenance of web articles posted in reverse chronological order made the publishing process feasible to a much larger, less technical population. Ultimately, this resulted in the distinct class of online publishing that produces blogs we recognize today¹⁰.

By 2001, blogging was enough of a phenomenon that how-to manuals began to appear, primarily focusing on technique. The importance of the blogging community (and its relationship to larger society) increased rapidly. Established schools of journalism began researching blogging and noting the differences between journalism and blogging¹¹.

In October 2006, Tecnorati¹² declared that it was tracking more than 57 million blogs. In its annual State of the Blogosphere report it also claimed that the number of blogs were growing at a rate of over one lakh blogs every day all over the world. Erring on the side of caution, it may be safe to assume that by now there could be over 65 million blogs the world over. However, Tecnorati makes it clear that of these only about 55% of the blogs remain active i.e. only about 55% blogs receive at least one post in the last three months. At the same time, there are some 1.3 millions blog posts made every day.

These figures make the impact that blogs have on the lives of people the world over more fathomable. According to Technorati's report, a little more than 4,000 blogs constitute the blogging elite. They have higher post frequencies, and have been operating for more than a year and a half on an average. Some of these are full-fledge professional enterprises that post many, many times per day and behave increasingly like the mainstream media. They are in the business mainly for revenues. The people who work in these blogs wield "increasingly dramatic influence on our cultures and democracies, says Sirfy¹³.

Sirfy's report classifies the blogs into four authority categories low authority, middle authority, high authority and very high authority (elite) blogs. However, even a casual extrapolation of the figures from his sample show that more than 71% blogs receive an average of 12 posts a month, and another 26% (middle authority blogs) receive upto 18 posts a month. So, it may be safe to assume from here than these 97% blogs are being

maintained by non-professional bloggers. It may be further assumed that these 97% blog for personal reasons most of which are revolve around sharing information on their personal lives, jokes, incidents, topics of personal interests etc.

What Makes Blogs So Popular

At the beginning of this article, it was emphasized blogs as signifying democratization of communication as they predicate the individual his values, emotions, judgments, and most importantly the individual will and relationships.

Secondly, free software, pre-designed templates, and free web-space offered by enterprises like Wordpress, Blogger, Blogspot etc. though require virtually no prerequisite technical grounding, they do offer the prospects of getting through to unlimited world wide audience, making blogging quite an attractive medium.

Then there are other more oblique factors too. The concerns raised by Human Development Report (1999) over some key issues that affect the role played by that information technology in human development are as relevant to the blogosphere as its proliferation. These issues are: Connectivity Making available communication and computer hardware; Access Besides hardware connectivity, promoting the use of internet use through group access, as also keeping the technology in public domain by watching out against commercial interests; Capacity developing human skills for making use of the technology; Money finding resources to fund the knowledge society; and Content and creativity making available locally relevant news, views, culture and commerce, and adapting technology for needs of the underprivileged¹⁴.

In developing and under developed countries most of these issues are still as relevant today, as they were when listed almost a decade ago. However, the people on the darker side of the digital divide may not have yet seen light because of this development, the proliferation of blogs may, to some extent, have helped to deal with at least one of the nagging issues. Many marginalized communities and groups have, in the form of blogs, an equal opportunity to voice their views and concerns; and create and share content relevant to the community. In short, the blog as a phenomenon is inclusive; and thus its growing importance.

Sharing has long since been established as one of the basic human activities. Maslow's hierarchy of needs¹⁵ listed belongingness as one of the basic human needs. In his theory of motivation, McClelland¹⁶ (1961) said that people are motivated by one of three things: the need for achievement, the need for power or the need for affiliation. Persons motivated by the need for affiliation seek relationships and interactions with a variety of different types of people. Besides these two, research literature is abound on need for affiliation as important to human well being.

Researchers generally agree that there is a definite urge in people to share their emotional experiences whether positive or negative (Luminet et al, 2000; Zech et al., unpublished; Rime et al., 1994; Kulik et al., 1994)*. However, there is no consensus on whether or not sharing the experience helps in relieving the emotional load. Even as the popular belief is still that sharing of an unrecovered emotional experience helps relieve load, there is growing empirical evidence that this does not happen (Zech & Rimé, 2002, Study 2; Zech, 1999; Zech, 2000; Rimé et al., 1996; Zech et al, unpublished)*. However still there are studies that related opening up to physical well being (M. A. Greenberg et al, 1996) *. Reviewers of these studies generally concluded that "opening up" and expressing stress-related thoughts and feelings was associated with improved physical and mental health (Esterling, L'Abate, Murray, & Pennebaker, 1999; Littrell, 1998; Pennebaker, 1993, 1997; Smyth, 1998) *. However Zech (unpublished, available online)*, is not convinced.

The findings issued from these writing studies are often understood as supporting the view that "putting emotion into words" is conducive to emotional recovery and emotional relief. However, whereas the design of these studies allow one to conclude that there are some positive effects of "putting emotion into words" on health indices, it does not address the process through which such effects are achieved. This process might involve factors totally alien to a ventilation effect. For instance, it might be that putting emotions into words in a solitary session stimulates the need to be with others and to share one's emotions with them. The resulting increase in received social support could thus account for health improvements.

The possibility that the frequency of social

sharing differs for positive and negative emotions has also been investigated. In two separate studies, Rime' et al. (1991)* asked college students and older adults to describe four specific events. The events were classified a priori as having a positive or a negative valence. The proportions of positive and negative events which were shared were remarkably similar (positive events: 89% in study 1, 95% in Study 2; negative events: 89% in study 1, 94% in study 2). Results reported by Christophe and DiGiacomo (1995)* suggest that exposure to positive emotional episodes accelerates and enhances the social sharing effect.

Thus, being exposed to an emotional episode has a marked impact on seeking social contacts with others and on the cognitive activity related to the eliciting situation. Together, these two processes lead to the social sharing of emotion, in which individuals communicate openly with one or more others about the circumstances of the emotion-eliciting event and about their own feelings and emotional reactions. Various studies have suggested that emotional intensity provides a good (if not complete) explanation for variations in extent of social sharing, and that the relation between emotional intensity and social sharing is not a linear function. In other words, emotional experiences do lead to social sharing, although the intensity of the experience may not effect the amount or the extent of sharing.

Further, it is clear that like other media of communication, blogging too helps to fulfill a person's innate need for sharing and affiliation. It is not yet however established, whether or not blogging as a means of affiliation is more gratifying than other means, or if it is more preferable than other means. It is also not yet clear if affiliation is the only reason why people blog. There have been studies on why people use various other media like television, radio, internet in general or for example internet chat in particular, and even why do they use mobile phones, besides of course, communication. The Uses and Gratifications¹⁷ approach in communication studies has put forth several interesting reasons for why people use various media, besides of course affiliation.

In all, the Gratifications research has been influenced by the basic need model suggested in two earlier studies. In 1972, McQuail, Blumler and Brown extended Lasswell's four groups 25 years later and have grouped these motives or needs for

watching television news as follows: Surveillance Information about things, which might affect one or will help one do or accomplish something; Diversion Escape from routine problems; emotional release; Personal Identity or Individual Psychology Value reinforcement or reassurance; self-understanding; reality exploration; Personal Relationship Social utility of information in conversation; substitution of media for companionship.

In a 1973 study, Katz, Gurevitch and Haas, saw the mass media as a means by which individuals connect or disconnect themselves with others (in Katz et al, 1974). They developed 35 needs taken from the largely speculative literature on the social and psychological functions of the mass media and put them into five categories: Cognitive needs Acquiring information, knowledge and understanding; Affective needs Emotion, pleasure, and feelings; Personal integrative needs Credibility, stability, and status; Social integrative needs Affiliation to family and friends; Tension release needs Escape and diversion.

Although, the Uses and Gratifications research started with the conventional media, especially television, it was slowly adapted to other burgeoning technologies, especially the new communication technologies.

December (1996) identified "communication, interaction, and information" as the three broad categories for why people use the Internet. Charney (1996) concluded from a study of university students that the Internet is used "to keep informed, for entertainment and diversion, to maintain communication, and to look at the sights and sounds of the 'Net" (p. 88), but most frequently for entertainment-diversion (p.90). In a pilot study conducted by Hyunoh Yoo (1996) the author found six gratifications dimensions relating to use of the Internet: "Entertainment, Information, Sociability-building, Sociability-maintaining, Transaction-general, and Transaction-task". Of these, entertainment, information, transaction-general, and sociability-building were related to WWW usage. Hunter (n.d.), writing about uses and gratifications of the WWW, cited three gratifications: browsing, information seeking, and entertainment. A 1995 study of college students' WWW usage resulted in "six motivational categories: entertainment, social interaction, pass time, escape, information, and Web site preference" (Kaye, 1998, p. 34).

According to the 9th WWW User Survey conducted by Georgia Tech (GVU's 9th WWW user survey, 1998), the WWW's youngest users (11-20) use the web mainly for "entertainment" (81%), "education" (70%), "time wasting" (67%), and "personal information" (60%). In a study (1996-97) of the gratifications received from Internet by a college faculty, staff and students, Hunter found that the primary use of e-mail was communication, whereas WWW was used for three major functions: entertainment, academic research and browsing. Usenet was used primarily for research purposes besides entertainment.

The similar studies exclusively on blogosphere are yet to be conducted. But like other internet applications, and other media, there sure are other reasons why so many people are getting hooked on to blogging. Extending our earlier assumptions, other motivations for blogging (besides affiliation) could be the need for achievement and need for power¹⁸. Or as per Maslow's need hierarch, other reasons for blogging could be the need for Esteem and Self-Actualisation. It is possible that why people blog is because they want to share, and they are looking for affiliation, self esteem, self actualization, and also they want to feel the power of influencing other people's views and thoughts.

Conclusions

From the preceding discussion, we may conclude that there are no easy answers to why people blog. Empirical data clearly shows that a millions of users world wide are regularly exposed to one blog or the other the experience may at times be un-identifiable from that on the World Wide Web. However, a majority are conscious and regular users of the blogosphere. Many of these blogs are extensions of personal diaries or accounts a ventilation outlet for the inner feelings on topics which could be as varied as Advocacy (for certain issue), or comments on Art and Photography; Automobiles and Gadgets; Dreams and the Supernatural; Fashion, Style, Shopping; Food and Restaurants; Friends ; Games; Goals, Plans, Hopes; Jobs, Work, Careers; Life; Movies, TV, Celebrities; Music; News and Politics; Parties and Nightlife; Pets and Animals; Quiz/Survey; Religion and Philosophy; Romance and Relationships; School and College life; Sports; Travel and Places; Writing and Poetry. One has to just as much as think about a topic and search the blogosphere. This multiplicity of voices and choices makes the phenomenon of blog a truly democratic medium.

This freedom is in itself a corollary of what this writer thinks to be the most important feature of the blog (and may also provide answers to why people blog) it preserves the individuality. Sharing and affiliation may be the chief motivators for a blogger, but so may be the needs for self esteem and self actualization. When people blog, they could be looking for all these and that too in an environment that promises to preserve that what they value most their individual self.

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